

Sluice Gates and Bago - Sittaung Canal in Bago District

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Abstract

Bago District in lower Myanmar is flourishing in agriculture but geographically , it is an area affected by flood. For this reason, the government has been continually building dams, reservoirs and sluice gates. Therefore, Shwehle sluice gate and Paingkyon sluice gate are built in Kawa Township. Tarwa sluice gate is built in Tanatpin Township. Shan Khaing sluice gate, Moe Yunn Gyi sluice gate and Naga Pauk sluice gate are built in Waw Township. Moreover Moe Yunn Gyi sluice gate, Tarwa sluice gate and Naga Pauk sluice gate are mainly connected with Bago - Sittaung Canal. This Canal is connected Bago river from near Tarwa Village in Thanatpin Township to Sittaung river near Myitkyo Village in Waw Township. Tarwa sluice gate in the side of Bago river and Myitkyo sluice gate in the side of Sittaung river from the start and end of canal were built on a level the water level. Four drainages were also built in the canal. These sluice gates and Bago- Sittaung Canal were built for the development of agriculture and prevention of flood.

Keywords : prevention of flood, salty water entering, keep fresh water, development of agriculture

Introduction

Bago District is formed with Bago township, Thanapin township, Kawa township, Waw township, Daik-U township, Nyaunglaybin township, Shwekyin township and Kyaukdaga township. The main economy of Bago District is agriculture and rice and other crops are mainly grown in the district. About 50 kinds of crops are grown in the district. The main rivers, which pass through Bago district are Bago river and Sittaung river. The fertile land in Bago District is Bago Yoma Mountain in the west and has become low as fertile plains in the east. Bago District has sufficient rainfall, that plain can be found especially in the raining season. Floods in the cultivated lands usually occurred in Bago District because of the overflowing of water in Bago and Sittaung rivers which causes the destruction of crops . For this reason, the government has been continually building dams, reservoirs and sluice gates to prevent overflowing and salty water entering into cultivated lands since 1988.

Objectives

- To share the Irrigation system in Bago District
- To share the important part of sluice gates and Bago-Sittaung Cannal

Bago District was formed with Bago Township, Thanapin Township, Kawa Township , Waw Township , Nyaunglaybin Township, Kyauktaga Township, Dauk -U Township and Shwekyin Township. The main economy of Bago District is agriculture and rice and other crops are mainly grown in the district. About 50 kinds of crops are grown in the district. The main rivers, which pass through Bago District are Bago River and Sittaung River. The fertile Bago District has Bago Yoma Mountain in the west and has become low fertile plain in the east. Bago District has sufficient rainfall that plains can be found especially in the raining season. Floods in the cultivated lands usually occurred in Bago District because of the overflow of water in Bago and Sittaung Rivers which cause destruction of crops. For this

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reason, the government has been continually built dams, reservoirs and sluice gates to prevent overflow and salt water into cultivated lands.

Shwehle sluice gate was built by blocking Hsema Creek at the junction of Bago River and Hsema Creek in Kawa Township. The building of Shwehle sluice gate project was allowed at the Meeting of Special Projects Implementation on 30 June 2003 and started to implement this project by the supervision of a director from No.6 Special Projects Implementation and an assistant director from Department of Irrigation on 1 December 2002-2003. The Shwehle sluice gate construction project was finished on 31 December 2003-2004 and the opening ceremony of this sluice gate was held on 24 February 2004. This sluice gate was a type of concrete gate.¹

The building of this sluice gate is to extract surplus water flow to Hsema Creek in the raining season to Bago River when Bago River has low water and to prevent sea water to overflow ground when the Bago River is overflow. It also prevents entering salty water and silt from the tide of Bago River into Hsema Creek in the summer. At the same time, Shwehle sluice gate could keep fresh water for summer cultivation. The areas who could feed for the summer cultivation are 35,000 acres of cultivated land.² The construction of Shwehle sluice gate was fruitful and helpful project for the development of economy, agriculture in Bago District and the country.³

Figure (1) Shwehle Sluice Gate

Paingkyon sluice gate is built at the junction between Bago River and Paingkyon Creek in Kawa Townshiop, Bago District. Paingkyon sluice gate construction project was allowed to carry out at the Meeting of Special Projects Implementation on 3 July 2000. The construction of this sluice gate was carrying out by No. 6 Construction Team Directorate Office from Department of Irrigation on 1 November 2000 and finished in 2002. The opening ceremony of

¹ ရွှေလှေ့ရေထိန်းတံခါး အစီရင်ခံစာ (Report of Shwehle Sluice Gate), March 2014, Limited Issue, Bago, Irrigation Department, Ministry of Agriculture and Irrigation Department, Republic of Union of Myanmar, March. 2014,P. 1.

² Ibid, P.3 .

³ Ibid, P.2.

Paingkyon sluice gate was held on 24 February 2002.¹ This sluice gate was a type of concrete sluice gate.

The construction of Paingkyon sluice gate was to drain surplus water from Paingkyon Creek in the raining season into Bago River when the water of Bago River is decreased and to prevent sea water into cultivated lands when the Bago River is overflow. It also prevents sea water and silt entering into Paingkyon Creek with this sluice gate and keeps fresh water for the summer cultivation at the same time.² Paingkyon sluice gate could feed water to over 30,000 acres of irrigated lands.³ Thus sluice gate is beneficial for the development of agriculture, economy and local people.

Figure (2) Paingkyon Sluice Gate

Tarwa sluice gate is situated at the junction of Bago-Sittaung Canal and Bago River in Thanatpin Township, Bago District. The construction of Tarwa sluice gate project was started at the Meeting of Special Projects Implementation on 1 July 2000 and the construction project of this sluice gate was started by Directorate Office of No. 6 Construction Team from Department of Irrigation on 1 October 2001 and finished on 25 December 2002. The opening ceremony of Tarwa sluice gate was held on 30 December 2002.⁴ The sluice gate is also a kind of concrete sluice gate.

The construction of Tarwa sluice gate could extract surplus water flows from Bago-Sittaung Canal in the raining season to Bago River when Bago River has low water and to prevent sea water to overflow ground when the Bago River is overflow. This sluice gate also prevents entering salty water and silt from the tide of Bago River to Bago-Sittaung Canal in the summer. At the same time, Tarwa sluice gate could keep fresh water for summer cultivation.

¹ ပိုင်ကျိုရေထိန်းတံခါး အစီရင်ခံစာ (Report of Paingkyon Sluice Gate), Limited Issue, Bago, Irrigation Department, Ministry of Agriculture and Irrigation Department, Republic of Union of Myanmar, March 2014, Limited Issue, P. 1.

² Ibid, P. 2 .

³ Ibid, P. 3.

⁴ တာဝရေထိန်းတံခါး အစီရင်ခံစာ (Report of Tarwa Sluice Gate), Limited Issue, Bago, Irrigation Department, Ministry of Agriculture and Irrigation Department, Republic of Union of Myanmar, March 2014, P. 2. (Hereafter cited as *Tarwa Sluice Gate*)

The areas who could feed for the summer cultivation from Tarwa sluice gate are 32,000 acres of cultivated land.¹ The construction of Tarwa sluice gate was fruitful and helpful project for the development of economy, agriculture in Bago District and the country.²

Figure (3) Tarwa Sluice Gate

Shan Kaing sluice gate is located at the junction between Shan Kaing drainage and Sittaung River near Shan Kaing Village in Waw Township, Bago District. Shan Kaing sluice gate construction project was allowed to carry out at the Meeting of Special Projects Implementation on 23 July 2000 to develop agricultural cultivation in the areas. However, the construction of this Shan Kaing sluice gate had been started since 1999-2000 Financial Years. The construction of this sluice gate was carrying out by No. 6 Construction Team Directorate Office from Department of Irrigation on 5 February 2000 and finished in 2000-2001. The opening ceremony of this Shan Kaing sluice was held on 25 March 2001.³

The purposes of the construction of Shan Kaing sluice gate were to drain the water from the overflow lands in Waw Township and to prevent water from Sittaung River and to prevent salty water and silt which rise together with tide from Sittaung River and to keep fresh water for summer cultivation. This sluice gate was an concrete sluice gate which is very supportive for the development of agricultural cultivation to the local people.⁴

¹ *Tarwa Sluice Gate* P.2.

² *Ibid*, P. 3 .

³ ရှမ်းကိုင်းရေထိန်းတံခါး အစီရင်ခံစာ (*Report of Shan Kaing Sluice Gate*), March 2014, Limited Issue, Bago, Irrigation Department, Ministry of Agriculture and Irrigation Department Republic of Union of Myanmar, March 2014, P. 1.

⁴ *Ibid*, P.4.

Figure (4) Shan Kaing Sluice Gate

Moe Yunn Gyi sluice gate is situated at 9 miles 2 furlongs of attached dam of Moe Yunn Gyi reservoir near Kywete Su Village in Waw Township, Bago District. The construction of this sluice gate was carrying out by No. 6 Construction Team headed by two Assistant Directorate Offices from Department of Irrigation in 2003-2004 and finished in 2005-2006. The opening ceremony of Moe Yunn Gyi sluice gate was held on 21 July 2001. This sluice gate was built with steel and concrete.¹

The construction of Moe Yunn Gyi sluice gate by the Ministry of Agriculture and Irrigation aimed to prevent the flood which usually occurred to 40, 000 acres of land during the raining season and it could control to drain water from over 40 square miles area of water of Moe Yunn Gyi reservoir. This sluice gate also drains water to the drainages in Bago-Sittaung Canal for summer cultivation and for storage of water in Waw and Thanatpin Townships. Moreover, Moe Yunn Gyi reservoir, which is connected with Pagaing Tar (Pagaing Embarkment) in Bago District, is intended to reduce and level the surplus water from Moe Yunn Gyi reservoir in the raining season and supply water for paddy cultivation after raining season and water for the greenery of 30 miles around Yangon. The construction of Moe Yunn Gyi sluice gate is beneficial project for the development of agriculture, economy and local people².

¹ မိုးယွန်းဂြီးရေထိန်းတံခါး အစီရင်ခံစာ (Report of Moe Yunn Gyi Sluice Gate), March 2014, Limited Issue, Bago, Irrigation Department, Ministry of Agriculture and Irrigation Department Republic of Union of Myanmar, March 2014, P.1.

² *Ibid*, P. 3.

Figure (5) Moe Yunn Gyi Sluice Gate

Naga Pauk sluice gate is located between Naga Pauk Creek near Myitkyo Town in Waw Township and the junction between Khamon and Myitkyo River.¹ The type of sluice gate is steel and concrete structure with flap gate. The construction of Naga Pauk sluice gate was implemented by Department of Irrigation in 2006-2007 according to the decision made at the Meeting of Special Projects Implementation and finished in 2009-2010. The opening ceremony of Naga Pauk sluice gate was held on 20 June 2009. It is a type of concrete Sluice gate.²

The construction of Naga Pauk sluice gate could prevent the overflow of Sittaung River to cultivated lands in the raining season in some degree, keep fresh water for irrigate filed in the summer until the end of January and prevent the intrusion of salty water from Sittaung River in March during summer. Moreover, this sluice gate could prevent deposition of silt together with the tide of Sittaung River which could prevent extinction of creek and dykes and flood. This sluice gate could keep surplus water from Kawliya, Bienda and Bawni reservoirs which are built for the greenery of 30 miles around Yangon and it could supply water to Bago-Sittaung Canal through Pagaingtar sluice gate which could increase the numbers of cultivated lands.³

Figure (6) Naga Pauk Sluice Gate

¹ နဂါးပေါက်ရေထိန်းတံခါး အစီရင်ခံစာ (Report of Naga Pauk Sluice Gate), March 2014, Limited Issue, Bago, Irrigation Department, Ministry of Agriculture and Irrigation Department, Republic of Union of Myanmar, March 2014, P.1.

² *Ibid*, P.3.

³ *Ibid*, P.2.

In the colonial Period Bago-Sittaung Canal was built to float teak rafts extracted from the forests of Pyinmana, Taungoo, Shwe Kyin in the east of Bago Region and from northern forests in Bago Region along Sittaung River to Yangon. This canal was built from 1873 to 1878. This canal is connected Bago River from near Tarwa Village in Thanatpin Township to Sittaung River near Myitkyo Village in Waw Township. It is 37 miles 7 furlongs long with an average of 50 feet at the mouth and 10 feet in depth.¹

The dam from 0/0 mile of canal in Tarwa Village to 8 miles 4 furlongs in Thanatpin Township along Bago-Sittaung Canal was regarded as precaution dam for flood. Tarwa sluice gate in the side of Bago River and Myitkyo sluice gate in the side of Sittaung River from the start and end of canal were built to level the water level which was 30 feet wide for the entering and going out of boats. Four drainages were also built in the canal to put out surplus water when the water is overflow in the raining season. These four drainages are Kyaikpadaing drainage, Bagan-Nyaungpin drainage, Min Ywa drainage, and Abyar-Shan Kaing drainage. Moreover, Myitkyo drainage was built to supply water into Bago-Sittaung Canal to run boats well when the water level is low in the summer².

Bago-Sittaung Canal supply water from Kodukwe Dam, Salu Dam and Shwe Laung Dam to Zaungtu Dam and thence from No. 2 Arm Drainage of Zaungtu Dam to Moe Yunn Gyi reservoir. The water from Moe Yunn Gyi reservoir is supplied to Bago-Sittaung Canal through Moe Yunn Gyi sluice gate and then provides water to Greenery drainage of 30 miles in Waw, Thanatpin, Kawa Townships and Khayan - Thone Kwa for summer paddy cultivation. When water from Sittaung River is used, it is tested not to have any salty water. Moreover, water from Wahkatok Dam is drained to Moe Yunn Gyi Lake and this water is used for summer paddy cultivation through Bago-Sittaung Canal.³ Thus, the distribution of water from Bago-Sittaung Canal is mainly connected with Kodukwe Dam, Salu Dam and Shwe Laung Dam and Zaungtu Dam. Moreover, Moe Yunn Gyi sluice gate, Naga Pauk Sluice gate and Tarwa sluice gate are connected with each other. The construction of Sluice gate are beneficial projects for the development of agriculture, economy and transportation in the Bago District.

¹ ပဲခူး-စစ်တောင်းတူးမြောင်း (Bago-Sittaung Canal), p. 1 (Hereafter cited as Bago-Sittaung Canal), Bago, Irrigation Department, Ministry of Agriculture and Irrigation Department, February 1914, P.1.

² *Ibid*, P.2.

³ Interviewed to U Myo Tint, Drawer Grade I, Assistant Director Office, Department of Irrigation and Water Supply, Bago Township on 29 October 2019.

Figure (7) Drainage from Zaungtu Dam to Greenery drainage of 30 miles
Source: Irrigation Department in Bago

Figure (8) Bago - Sittaung Canal Location Map

Source: Irrigation Department in Bago

Figure (9) Myitkyo Sluice Gate

Source: Irrigation Department in Bago

Conclusion

The Bago District has sufficient rainfall and it can be found especially in the raining season. Floods in the cultivated land usually occurred in Bago District because of the overflowing of water in Bago river and Sittaung river. Therefore the government has been building dams, reservoirs and sluice gates to prevent overflow , salty water entering into cultivated lands and silt from the tide of Bago river and Sittaung river in summer and to keep fresh water for summer cultivation. The construction of Sluice gates are beneficial projects for the development of agriculture and economy in Bago District.

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ရွှေလှေရေထိန်းတံခါးအစီရင်ခံစာ (*Report of Shwehle Sluice Gate*), Bago Irrigation Department, Ministry of Agriculture and Irrigation Department, Republic of Union of Myanmar, March 2014.

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